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Extension of Heron's Formula to a Spherical Triangle

Open Mathematics Collaboration*

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Abstract

We present an extension of the classical Heron's formula, traditionally applied to planar triangles for calculating their areas, to spherical triangles formed by great circles on a sphere. We begin with a review of preliminary concepts and some fundamental results in spherical geometry, after which we develop the spherical version of Heron's formula.

keywords: spherical geometry, spherical triangle, Heron's formula

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Introduction

1. This article primarily relies on references [1–3].
2. Geometry is a fundamental area of Mathematics and provides essential tools for problem-solving. Among these tools, Heron's formula stands out, used in plane geometry to calculate the area of a triangle based on the lengths of its sides, without needing to know its internal angles. This formula is attributed to the Greek mathematician Heron of Alexandria

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3. The application of Heron's formula is restricted to Euclidean geometry, where triangles are defined on a plane, and the sum of their internal angles is exactly 180 degrees. When we change the study environment to a sphere, spherical geometry emerges, which presents some challenges. In spherical triangles, formed by great circles on a sphere, the sum of the internal angles exceeds 180 degrees, preventing the direct application of the classical Heron's formula and highlighting the need for an adapted version of this formula.
4. Spherical geometry has numerous applications, especially in fields such as geodesy, astronomy, navigation, and cartography, where problems arise that require the use of spherical triangles to calculate, for instance, areas and distances between reference points. For this reason, extending Heron's formula to spherical triangles offers a valuable tool for professionals in these fields.
5. There are various formulas to calculate the area of spherical triangles. The search for an analogous version of Heron's formula is justified by the simplicity that the plane formula provides. The classical version of Heron's formula stands out for providing a direct solution based on the triangle's sides, without the need for complex angular calculations.
6. In this paper, we propose an extension of Heron's formula for spherical triangles and provide a detailed derivation. We begin by presenting the classical version of Heron's formula, followed by a review of fundamental concepts in spherical geometry, establishing the necessary foundation for extending the formula. Finally, we present the mathematical derivation of the spherical version of Heron's formula.

Preliminaries

The Classical Heron's Formula

7. Let $\triangle ABC$ be a planar triangle with sides of lengths a , b and c . If $s = (a + b + c)/2$, which represents its semiperimeter, then the area of $\triangle ABC$ is given by

$$\text{Area} (\triangle ABC) = \sqrt{s(s - a)(s - b)(s - c)}$$

(see [1, Proposição 7.30]).

Spherical Geometry

8. Let O be a point in space and r a positive real number. The sphere with center O and radius r is the set of all points in space which lie at distance r from O .
9. Let S be a sphere with center O and Γ a plane in space:
If $\Gamma = \Gamma_1$ passes through O then the intersection of Γ_1 and S is called a *great circle* of the sphere.
If $\Gamma = \Gamma_2$ lies at a distance $0 < d < r$ from O , then the intersection of Γ_2 and S is called a *small circle*.
10. Two distinct points A and B on a sphere S are called *antipodal* if the line ℓ connecting them passes through the center of the sphere.
11. If two distinct points A and B on a sphere S are not antipodal, there exists a unique great circle passing through both A and B , which is denoted by $\bigcirc AB$ (see [2, Axiom 9.7]).
12. For two points A and B on a sphere that are not antipodal, the *spherical arc* \widehat{AB} is defined as the set consisting of A , B , and all points on the great circle $\bigcirc AB$ that lie between A and B .
13. Let A and B be two points on a sphere that are not antipodal. The *spherical ray* \overrightarrow{AB} is defined as the set of all points C on the great circle $\bigcirc AB$ such that C is on \widehat{AB} or B is between A and C . The point A is referred to as the *vertex or endpoint* of the spherical ray.
14. Let A , B and C be points on a sphere that do not lie on the same great circle. The *spherical angle* $\sphericalangle ABC$, with B as its *vertex*, is defined as the union of the spherical rays \overrightarrow{BA} and \overrightarrow{BC} . These rays are called the *sides* of the angle. The *interior* of the angle is the region formed by the intersection of two hemispheres: one is the side of the great circle $\bigcirc AB$ containing C , and the other is the side of the great circle $\bigcirc BC$ containing A .

Figure 1: Spherical angle $\sphericalangle ABC$.

Spherical Triangles

15. Consider three points A , B , and C on a sphere that do not lie on the same great circle. The *spherical triangle* $\Delta^s ABC$ is defined as the union of the three spherical arcs \widehat{AB} , \widehat{BC} , and \widehat{AC} .

- The points A , B and C are called the *vertices* (singular: vertex) of $\Delta^s ABC$.
- The arcs \widehat{AB} , \widehat{BC} and \widehat{AC} are referred to as the *sides* of $\Delta^s ABC$.
- The spherical angles $\sphericalangle CAB$, $\sphericalangle ABC$ and $\sphericalangle BCA$, also denoted by $\sphericalangle A$, $\sphericalangle B$ and $\sphericalangle C$, are the *angles* of $\Delta^s ABC$.

Figure 2: Spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$.

16. **Theorem 1.** (See [2, Theorem 13.2]). In a spherical triangle, the sum of the measures of its angles is greater than π radians (180°).

17. **Theorem 2.** (See [2, Theorem 14.4]). The area of a spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$ is given by the formula:

$$\text{Area}(\Delta^s ABC) = (m \sphericalangle A + m \sphericalangle B + m \sphericalangle C - \pi) r^2,$$

where $m \sphericalangle A$, $m \sphericalangle B$ and $m \sphericalangle C$ represent the measures of the angles of the triangle and r denotes the radius of the sphere.

18. In a spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$, the *spherical excess* is defined as $2E$, where E is given by

$$E = \frac{m \sphericalangle A + m \sphericalangle B + m \sphericalangle C - \pi}{2}.$$

19. **Notations:** For a spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$, the following notation will be used in the subsequent results:

- A , B and C represent the measures of the angles at vertices A , B and C , respectively;
- a , b and c represent the lengths of the sides opposite to vertices A , B and C , respectively;
- $s = (a + b + c)/2$ represents its semiperimeter.

Note that the letters A , B and C may sometimes refer to points and, at other times, to the measures of angles.

20. **Theorem 3 (Delambre's Analogies, see [2, 3]).** In any spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$, the following analogies hold:

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A-B)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A-B)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

21. **Theorem 4 (Euler's Formula, see [2]).** Let E be one-half of the spherical excess of a spherical triangle, given by: $E = \frac{A+B+C-\pi}{2}$. Then

$$\cos(E) = \frac{1 + \cos(a) + \cos(b) + \cos(c)}{4 \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)}.$$

22. **Theorem 5 (Cagnoli's Formula).** Let E be one-half of the spherical excess of a spherical triangle, given by: $E = \frac{A+B+C-\pi}{2}$. Let $s = \frac{a+b+c}{2}$ represent the semiperimeter of the spherical triangle. Then we have:

$$\sin(E) = \frac{\sqrt{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}}{2 \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)}.$$

23. We can prove Theorem 5 using the identity $\sin(E) = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2(E)}$ and Euler's formula presented in (21).

24. Indeed, setting $T = \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)$, we have

$$\sin^2(E) = 1 - \cos^2(E) = \frac{(4T)^2 - ((1 + \cos(a) + \cos(b) + \cos(c)))^2}{(4T)^2}.$$

25. Thus,

$$\sin^2(E) = \frac{16 \cos^2\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos^2\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos^2\left(\frac{c}{2}\right) - ((1 + \cos(a) + \cos(b) + \cos(c)))^2}{(4T)^2}.$$

26. Applying the identity $\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) = \frac{1+\cos(\theta)}{2}$, the second term simplifies to

$$\frac{2(1 + \cos(a))(1 + \cos(b))(1 + \cos(c)) - ((1 + \cos(a) + \cos(b) + \cos(c)))^2}{(4T)^2}.$$

27. Using the identity $\cos(2\theta) = 2 \cos^2(\theta) - 1$, we simplify the above expression further, obtaining

$$\sin^2(E) = \frac{-\cos(2a) - 2 \cos^2(b) + 4 \cos(a) \cos(b) \cos(c) - \cos(2c)}{32T^2}.$$

28. On the other hand,

$$\frac{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}{(2T)^2} = \frac{\sin(\frac{1}{2}(a+b+c)) \sin(\frac{1}{2}(b+c-a)) \sin(\frac{1}{2}(a+c-b)) \sin(\frac{1}{2}(a+b-c))}{(2T)^2}$$

29. Applying the identity, $\sin(\theta) \sin(\beta) = \frac{1}{2} (\cos(\theta - \beta) - \cos(\theta + \beta))$, we obtain

$$\frac{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}{(2T)^2} = \frac{\frac{1}{4}(\cos(a) - \cos(b+c))(\cos(b) - \cos(a+c))}{(2T)^2}.$$

30. Expanding the product, the second term reduces to

$$\frac{\frac{1}{4}(\cos(a) \cos(b) - \cos(a) \cos(a+c) - \cos(b+c) \cos(b) + \cos(b+c) \cos(a+c))}{(2T)^2}.$$

31. Using the identity, $\cos(\theta) \cos(\beta) = \frac{1}{2} (\cos(\theta - \beta) + \cos(\theta + \beta))$, we simplify further

$$\frac{\frac{1}{4}[\frac{1}{2}(\cos(a-b) + \cos(a+b)) - \frac{1}{2}(\cos(c) + \cos(2a+c)) - \frac{1}{2}(\cos(c) + \cos(2b+c)) + \frac{1}{2}(\cos(b-a) + \cos(2c+a+b))]}{(2T)^2}.$$

32. Simplifying and applying $\cos(2\theta) = 2 \cos^2(\theta) - 1$, we conclude

$$\frac{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}{(2T)^2} = \frac{-\cos(2a) - 2 \cos^2(b) + 4 \cos(a) \cos(b) \cos(c) - \cos(2c)}{32T^2}.$$

33. Thus, from (27) and (32), we deduce

$$\sin^2(E) = \frac{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}{(2T)^2}.$$

34. Therefore,

$$\sin(E) = \frac{\sqrt{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}}{2 \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)}.$$

□

35. **Theorem 6 (Breitschneider's Analogies).** In any spherical triangle $\triangle^s ABC$, the following analogies hold:

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right) \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right) \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)},$$

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

36. To demonstrate these analogies, we use Delambre's analogies presented in (20).

37. **Proof of the First Analogy:** To prove the first analogy of Theorem 6, subtract 1 from both sides of the fourth analogy in(20),

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} - 1 = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} - 1.$$

38. By (18), $\frac{A+B}{2} = E - \frac{C}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}$. Thus,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(E - \frac{C}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

39. Expanding further,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\left(\frac{C}{2} - \frac{E}{2}\right) - \frac{E}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\left(\frac{C}{2} - \frac{E}{2}\right) + \frac{E}{2}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

40. Simplifying,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{-2\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

41. On the other hand, note that $\frac{a+b}{2} = s - \frac{c}{2}$. Hence,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(s - \frac{c}{2}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

42. Expanding,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{s}{2} + \left(\frac{s}{2} - \frac{c}{2}\right)\right) - \cos\left(-\frac{s}{2} + \left(\frac{s}{2} - \frac{c}{2}\right)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

43. This simplifies to

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} = \frac{-2\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

44. Combining results from (37)), (40) and (43), we conclude

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

45. **Proof of the Second Analogy:** To prove the second analogy of Theorem 6, add 1 to both sides of the fourth analogy in (20),

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} + 1 = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a+b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} + 1.$$

46. Using steps similar to those in the proof of the first analogy, we obtain

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

47. **Proof of the Third Analogy:** To prove the third analogy of Theorem 6, subtract 1 from both sides of the first analogy in (20),

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} - 1 = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} - 1.$$

48. As $\frac{A+B}{2} = E - \frac{C}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}$, we have

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(E - \frac{C}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

49. Expanding further,

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\left(\frac{C}{2} - \frac{E}{2}\right) - \frac{E}{2}\right) - \cos\left(\left(\frac{C}{2} - \frac{E}{2}\right) + \frac{E}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

50. Simplifying this expression yields,

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{2\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)}.$$

51. On the other hand, as $\frac{a-b}{2} = \frac{(s-b)}{2} - \frac{(s-a)}{2}$ and $\frac{c}{2} = \frac{(s-a)}{2} + \frac{(s-b)}{2}$, we have

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b) - \frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a) + \frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

52. Simplifying,

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right) - \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} = \frac{2\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

53. Combining results from (47)), (50) and (52), we conclude

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

54. **Proof of the Fourth Analogy:** To prove the fourth analogy of Theorem 6, add 1 to both sides of the first analogy in (20),

$$\frac{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(A+B)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} + 1 = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(a-b)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)} + 1.$$

55. Following steps similar to the proof of the third analogy, we arrive at

$$\frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}C\right)} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right)\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}c\right)}.$$

□

56. **Theorem 7 (Lhuilier's Formula).** In any spherical triangle $\triangle^s ABC$,

$$\tan\left(\frac{E}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\tan\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{s-a}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{s-b}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{s-c}{2}\right)}.$$

57. To prove Lhuilier's Formula, we use Breitschneider's analogies presented in (35).

58. From Theorem 6, dividing the first analogy by the second, we obtain

$$\frac{\tan\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right) \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)} = \tan\left(\frac{1}{2}s\right) \tan\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-c)\right).$$

59. Similarly, dividing the third analogy by the fourth, we get

$$\frac{\tan\left(\frac{1}{2}E\right) \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{1}{2}(C-E)\right)} = \tan\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-b)\right) \tan\left(\frac{1}{2}(s-a)\right).$$

60. Now, multiplying the equalities from (58) and (59), we have

$$\tan^2\left(\frac{E}{2}\right) = \tan\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-a}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-b}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-c}{2}\right).$$

61. Taking the square root,

$$\tan\left(\frac{E}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\tan\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-a}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-b}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-c}{2}\right)}.$$

□

Extension of Heron's Formula

62. **Theorem 7 (Main Result).** Let $\Delta^s ABC$ be a spherical triangle with sides of lengths a , b and c , and semiperimeter $s = (a + b + c)/2$. Then the area of $\Delta^s ABC$ is given by:

$$\text{Area}(\Delta^s ABC) = 2 \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}}{2 \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)} \right) r^2,$$

or equivalently

$$\text{Area}(\Delta^s ABC) = 4 \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\tan\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-a}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-b}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-c}{2}\right)} \right) r^2,$$

where r is the radius of the sphere.

63. **Proof of the Extended Heron's Formula:** We begin the proof by noting that, from (17) and (18),

$$\text{Area}(\Delta^s ABC) = 2Er^2.$$

64. Using the above equation, the first formula for the area of the spherical triangle $\Delta^s ABC$ follows directly from Cagnoli's Formula (22), since

$$E = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sin(s) \sin(s-a) \sin(s-b) \sin(s-c)}}{2 \cos\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{b}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{c}{2}\right)} \right).$$

65. The second formula is obtained by applying the equality in (63) and using Lhuilier's Formula (56) to express E as

$$E = 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\tan\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-a}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-b}{2}\right) \tan\left(\frac{s-c}{2}\right)} \right).$$

□

Final Remarks

66. This article presents an extension of Heron's formula for spherical triangles, establishing it as an important theoretical tool in the field of spherical geometry. In addition to addressing the limitations of the classical Heron's formula in non-Euclidean contexts, the results obtained have practical applications in fields such as geodesy, astronomy, and cartography, where precise calculations of spherical areas are essential.
67. Formulas were derived for calculating the area of spherical triangles, offering simplified methods that eliminate the need for complex angular calculations. Particularly notable is the use of semiperimeters and trigonometric relationships, which make the calculations more accessible and efficient.
68. Furthermore, this research proposes the possibility of adapting other classical formulas from planar geometry to curved surfaces, such as spherical ones, thereby broadening their applicability to complex problems across various scientific disciplines.

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[6]

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